

CHANGES IN THE ORAL CAVITY OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLETE SECONDARY EDENTULISM.

ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ В ПОЛОСТИ РТА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ПОЛНОЙ ВТОРИЧНОЙ АДЕНТИЕЙ

TO'LIQ IKKILAMCHI TISHSIZLIGI BO'LGAN BEMORLARNING OG'IZ BO'SHLIG'IDAGI O'ZGARISHLAR

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Abstract. *The article discusses changes in the oral cavity of patients with complete secondary edentulism. changes in the oral cavity of patients with complete secondary edentulism, basic and additional methods of examination were carried out in 25 patients. Among those who participated in the survey, there are women and men. changes in the oral cavity of patients with complete secondary toothlessness, based on the methods of studying them, to solve the medical and social problem and to develop new technologies for effective complex treatment of patients with partial and complete absence of teeth there was a need to develop.*

Key words: *primary toothlessness, secondary toothlessness, congenital and acquired toothlessness, supple.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются изменения в полости рта у пациентов с полной вторичной адентией. Изменения в полости рта у пациентов с полной вторичной адентией, основные и дополнительные методы обследования проведены у 25 пациентов. Среди принявших участие в обследовании есть женщины и мужчины. изменения в полости рта у пациентов с полной вторичной беззубостью, на основе методов их изучения, для решения медико-социальной проблемы и разработки новых технологий эффективного комплексного лечения пациентов с частичным и полным отсутствием зубов возникла необходимость в разработке.*

Ключевые слова: *первичная беззубость, вторичная беззубость, врожденная и приобретенная беззубость, эластичность.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada to'liq ikkilamchi tishsizligi bo'lgan bemorlarning og'iz bo'shlig'idagi o'zgarishlar muhokama qilinadi. 25 bemorda to'liq ikkilamchi tishsizligi bo'lgan bemorlarning og'iz bo'shlig'idagi o'zgarishlar, asosiy va qo'shimcha tekshirish usullari o'tkazildi. So'rovda qatnashganlar orasida ayollar va erkaklar bor. To'liq ikkilamchi tishsiz bemorlarning og'iz bo'shlig'idagi o'zgarishlar, ularni o'rganish usullariga asoslanib, tibbiy-ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilish va tishlari qisman va to'liq yo'qligi bo'lgan bemorlarni samarali kompleks davolashning yangi texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish.*

Kalit so'zlar: *birlamchi tishsizlik, ikkilamchi tishsizlik, tug'ma va orttirilgan tishsizlik, elastiklik.*

Introduction: Discussion of changes in the oral cavity of patients with complete secondary edentulism and changes in the oral cavity in complete secondary adentia, basic and additional methods of examination Full changes in the oral cavity of patients without secondary teeth, based on the methods of their study.

Literature review: The following articles were used for the frequency and clinical manifestations of stomatitis in patients after acrylic prosthesis [6], poetic orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with acquired defects of the upper jaw [3], observation of prosthetic stomatitis in adults using ethacryl and fluorox prosthesis [1].

Research Methodology: The urgent problem of modern dentistry is to study toothlessness in patients, which is the cause of complete absence of teeth, to determine and prevent changes in the oral cavity of patients with complete secondary toothlessness, and orthopedic treatment.

Primary, genuine and congenital toothlessness - lack of development of tooth follicles or lysis due to some reason. In this type, the tooth does not erupt. When asked, the patient says that the tooth has not come out at all. Alveolar tissue atrophy occurs when the tooth cavity is formed. X-rays can show the absence of a tooth or its ridge.

Secondary, increased toothlessness - a tooth erupts and is lost for some reason. for example, caries and its complications, trauma, orthodontic indications.

False edentulism occurs when the tooth ridge does not develop initially or erupts late because it has stopped developing or remains in a state of retention. later the tooth may crack. therefore, it is also called false toothlessness.

Partial edentulousness occurs when 1 to 13 teeth are missing. depending on the level, it is divided into light, heavy and heavy types. Partial edentulousness is divided into types with preserved bite height (antagonist is preserved in the area of small and large food teeth) and non-preserved bite height (antagonist is lost in the area of small and large food teeth).

Complete edentulousness occurs when the teeth are completely lost. Complete edentulism is secondary in many cases.

Etiology - In some cases, toothlessness of the tooth row is caused by the lack of orthopedic treatment, trauma and chronic diseases, caries and its complications, orthodontic instructions and the influence of the living environment.

Clinic - when the teeth are completely lost, the third part of the face decreases, the nose-lip, chin folds develop, the progeny of old age develops. Aesthetic appearance, pronunciation disorder, loss of chewing gum, drooping of the corners of the mouth (angular folds), hearing loss, and jaw protrusion in severe cases.

The purpose of the study. identification of types of toothlessness, study and prevention in patients, taking into account changes in the oral cavity of patients with complete secondary toothlessness in orthopedic treatment. This method was tested in 25 patients. There are men and women among those who participated in the survey. All patients have a defect in the tooth row, that is, complete toothlessness.

Analysis and results: As a result of these investigations, 100% of our patients remained secondary edentulous. In patients with secondary edentulous clinical manifestations, after the loss of teeth in the dental row, changes in the relationship of form and function and clinical appearance, number, the role of the teeth in chewing, the types of relationship between the teeth, the condition of the periodontal and hard tissues of the remaining teeth, the patient's age and general condition, and the clinical appearance is different. All patients underwent basic and additional examination methods. Palpation is used to determine joint, muscle, alveolar septal atrophy, mucous membrane yielding area, torus and exostoses.

There are 4 types of mucous membrane of the supple prosthetic area:

- 1- Ideal mucosa
- 2- Hard mucous membrane
- 3- Soft mouth
- 4- coronal mucous membrane of the rooster

According to Lund, yielding areas of the upper jaw.

1-Saggital fork: palate fork;

2-Para saggital: alveolar obstruction;

3-fatty branch: anterior branch of the palatine cavity;

4-Glandular branch: posterior branch of the palatal cavity;

Conclusion. Determining the types of toothlessness and making a correct diagnosis, taking into account the changes in the oral cavity of patients with complete secondary toothlessness, helps to correctly approach orthopedic treatment.

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